

PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT – A THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

N.VANAJA

Research Scholar, Faculty of Management, SRMIST, KTR. Email: vanajamathi@gmail.com

Dr. P.S.RAJESWARI

Associate Professor, Faculty of Management, SRMIST, KTR. Email: psrajism@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Perceived Organizational Support (POS), which shows the organization's appreciation for employees' efforts and concern for employee benefits, is a crucial tool for businesses to use in order to build great relationships with employees and drive them to work hard. The goal of this paper is to give an outline of the point-of-sale concept as well as the factors that influence it. In addition, the study will use other research data to analyse the influence of positive POS. According to the data, perceived organisational support emphasizes the organization's commitment to employees and its unilateral interaction. Positive organizational support influences organisational behaviour, employee motivation, employee performance, employee engagement, employee commitment, employee loyalty, and overall productivity. The current study contributes to the employee-employer interaction in the workplace, making it socioeconomically significant.

Key words: Perceived Organizational Support, Factors of POS, Effects of positive POS

1. INTRODUCTION

Perceived organisational support refers to employees' impressions of how much their employer values their contribution and cares about their well-being (POS). POS has been found to have an impact on employee performance and well-being. The employee's perception of how much the company values and cares about them is referred to as POS. Employees regard their labour as a sort of reciprocal commerce that extends beyond a formal contract and displays relative dependency. Employees must assess whether and to what extent their employer will recognise and reward their efforts, support their socio-emotional needs, and provide assistance when they request it. According to organisational support theory, employees work harder to help their company achieve its goals in exchange for a high degree of support, delivering loyalty and effort in exchange for material and social rewards.

Definition of Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Employee perceptions of how much their company values and promotes their well-being are referred to as POS (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Based on the social exchange perspective (Blau, 1964) and the reciprocity norm, OST believes that employees have an internal obligation to reciprocate their organization's favourable and helpful treatment by forming favourable sentiments about it and aiding it in attaining its goals (Gouldner, 1960). (See, for example, Eisenberger et al., 1986). According to OST, POS satisfies employees' socio-emotional needs

(e.g., esteem), resulting in good attitudes and behaviours toward the organisation, as well as increased subjective well-being (e.g., Armeli et al., 1998; Kurtessis et al., 2017).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Perceived organisational support (POS) refers to employees' perceptions of how their employer values their contribution and cares about their well-being (Pierre, 2010). This exemplifies how a company's commitment to its employees can be tremendously advantageous. By instilling a general obligation among employees to care for and treat the organisation well, POS reflects the firm's good treatment (Clark, Mandilara, Ristig, & KÜRten, 2009). Employees will be held responsible for their work-related conduct. It will assist the organisation in achieving its various objectives.

Organizational support theory (OST), as proposed by James N. Kurtessis (2015), posits that employees form impressions of how much their employers value their contributions and care about their well-being. According to (Rhoades, 2002), there are three sorts of treatment from organisations that are viewed favourable and can improve organisational support perception.

Employees' perceptions of organisational support, according to Nurmalia Ariarni and Tri Wulida Afrianty (2017), have a positive impact on employee performance. According to Wu Wann-Yih (2011) and Mark C. Johlke (2003), there is a strong link between employee work performance and perceived organisational support. Perception Organizational Support, on the other hand, is unrelated to performance, according to Christina L. Stamper's results. This suggests that there is a research gap in this area, but the purpose of this study was to show how perceived organisational support affects employee performance.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In today's knowledge-based economy, employees are crucial. Employees are seen as important assets. As a result, the Human Resource Department's efforts to identify and analyse the elements that influence employee performance are a must if effectiveness and efficiency are to be ensured. According to the study, POS is associated with a number of positive outcomes for both the company and the individual, including conscientiousness in fulfilling regular work responsibilities, organisational commitment, and job satisfaction. As a result, employees' POS levels must be evaluated on a regular basis to ensure positive results for the organisation, which finally leads to profitability. In the absence of direct incentives, the company may take actions to increase employee POS in order to lower turnover and increase retention. As a result, the determinants of POS must be examined in order to put in place measures to improve POS. There is also evidence that companies that take steps to persuade employees that the company values their contributions and cares about their well-being can help to mitigate the demotivating effects of employee cynicism and scepticism. As a result, in order to take such steps, the level of POS must be investigated. Interventions that target the antecedents of POS are more likely to improve organisational commitment and the quality of employees' lives at work. As a result, a POS study is required to provide favourable outcomes for both the company and its employees.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To investigate the various influences on Perceived Organizational Support.
2. To investigate the link between antecedents, causes and perceived organisational support.
3. using existing research literature, determine the consequences of perceived organisational support.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The goal of this study is to discover the antecedent elements that influence POS. It also tries to investigate the impact of positive POS on organisational performance. The conceptual model that follows illustrates the study's overarching framework.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of Perceived Organizational Support

Source: Model developed by author

This model is developed to understand the concept of the study at a glance. The study is aimed to understand the antecedents of perceived organizational support and its influence in workplace by referring other research papers and articles. The study explains how to measure perceived organizational support and to understand its effect on job place. The study wants to analysis the impact of perceived organizational support in workplace. Further, the study aims to study how this perceived organizational support is beneficial to both employee and the organization. It is found that creating positive perceived organizational support motivates employee and make them happier, increase work performance and overall productivity.

Factors of POS

In today's competitive world, perceived organizational support is a critical construct with well-established organizational benefits. As a result, this article attempts to trace the characteristics that influence perceived organizational support in order to add value to the current study. The factors of POS can be divided into three categories, as follows:

1. Nature of Job

Scholars argue that POS is significantly influenced by management's voluntary actions rather than mandated by external entities or environmental conditions, based on social exchange

theory research; the four job characteristics typically considered are challenging work, autonomy, task variety, and perceived workload.

a. Workplace difficulty

A person's desire to be stimulated by their profession is reflected in their need for challenge, which can be measured by the degree to which the job necessitates a wide range of abilities. It is naturally satisfying to have the opportunity to do tough tasks.

b. Autonomy

Job satisfaction is determined by an individual's ability to plan work, establish what activities must be completed, and decide how effectively to carry out those responsibilities. The more autonomy a person has, the more responsible he or she will feel for the outcomes. Increased motivation, pleasure, and work performance have all been related to a sense of autonomy.

c. Task diversity

Because the workplace is full of unexpected or innovative events, future responsibilities are unknown and many of them are non-routine or cannot be clearly described ahead of time.

d. Assumed workload

Managers can strive to keep labour costs low by increasing employee workload and pushing them to work longer hours. High workload has a substantial negative correlation with POS.

2. Workplace Stress

Another aspect that occurs as a result of labour weariness, role ambiguity, and role conflict is job pressure.

a. Exhaustion from work

Software developers frequently deplete their emotional and mental energies in order to meet job demands. Work weariness and other psychosomatic symptoms have been linked to POS in the past.

b. Uncertainty about the role

Role ambiguity occurs when a person's instructions are unclear, imprecise, or insufficient. The effect of ambiguity on the POS relationship has been mixed, with one study indicating a strong negative association between POS and employment ambiguity. Some researchers stated that role ambiguity was a precursor to POS, while others suggested that POS was a mediator between role ambiguity and the desire to stay with an organisation.

c. Role incompatibility

The perception of incompatible or incongruent obligations put on an incumbent frequently leads to high role conflict, due to the requirement to meet the needs of a large number of clients, the constant usage of project teams, and fast changing technology or procedures. Although POS and role conflict have a substantial negative association, there may be a causal relationship

between the two, or POS may minimise the influence of role conflict on voluntary turnover intention.

3. Workplace values

Pay-for-performance, prizes, awards, and recognition can help management meet some of the employee support demands.

a. Performance pay, incentives, and awards

When it comes to keeping information technology personnel, state governments frequently emphasise on the need to increase pay scales. The company may be able to

b. Mentoring

Employee development activities that allow them to expand their skills have a positive impact on POS. Mentoring is a strategy used by some businesses to reduce employee turnover. There are two types of professional and psychosocial stress. Acceptance, role modelling, counselling, and friendship are among the first functions, while coaching, sponsorship, and protection are among the second. Mentors can provide social support, which appears to reduce the chances of quitting.

c. Motivation

Many characteristics of an employee's treatment by the organisation, according to Eisenberg, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa, influence the employee's interpretation of the organization's intentions underlying that treatment, which, in turn, influences the employee's perception of the organization's intentions underlying that treatment (1986: 501). "Positive discretionary support," according to Eisenberger and colleagues (1990), is the most important factor in determining perceived organisational support.

Effect of POS

Other types of performance, continuing commitment, and turnover all had tiny but statistically reliable correlations with POS.

a. Employee Commitment and Engagement

The overall impact of organisational commitment is enormous. The two sorts of commitment indicated in this category, as one might expect, have quite distinct relationships to POS. Although there was a high and positive link between POS and emotional commitment, there was a weak and negative link between POS and perseverance commitment. Even after outliers were removed, the effect sizes for both constructs were heterogeneous. Regardless, all of the investigations found POS–affective commitment associations to be positive. The association between POS and continuing commitment was more variable, ranging from near zero to significant and negative.

b. Job satisfaction

Job-related effects exhibited a substantial effect size overall. Job satisfaction and a good mood had significant and diverse effect sizes. Despite the fact that removing outliers did not completely reduce variability, all research that combined the two dimensions indicated moderate to large links in the predicted direction for work satisfaction and small to big connections in the predicted direction for pleasant mood.

c. Participation in the Workplace

The connection between POS and job involvement was shown to be moderately positive. By deleting one outlier, we were able to achieve effect size homogeneity while maintaining the moderate association.

d. Performance

The organisation had moderate linkages to POS and extra role performance, but no ties to the other areas of performance. After removing outliers, POS demonstrated consistent connections with all forms of performance.

e. Withdrawal Behaviour

In general, POS and withdrawal behaviour had a moderately negative connection. The strongest links were found between POS and the intention to stop, next POS and withdrawal behaviours before to turnover, and finally POS and actual turnover.

f. Organizational behaviours of employees

As a result, empirical evidence has shown that POS is positively related to a variety of positive work attitudes and behaviours, such as affective commitment (e.g., Eisenberger et al., 2001), organisational identification (e.g., Sluss et al., 2008), work engagement (e.g., Caesens et al., 2016), and job performance (e.g., Caesens et al., 2016). (e.g., Caesens et al., 2016). (See, for example, Caesens et al., 2016). Two instances are Chen et al., 2009, and Shoss et al., 2013. Overall health (e.g., Eisenberger et al., 1997; Caesens and Stinglhamber, 2014) have both been linked to POS (e.g., Eisenberger et al., 1997; Caesens and Stinglhamber, 2014). (e.g., Bradley and Cartwright, 2002). In numerous studies, POS has been shown to lower employee turnover intentions (e.g., Kurtessis et al., 2017), absenteeism (e.g., Eder and Eisenberger, 2008), and burnout (e.g., Kang et al., 2010; Caesens et al., 2010). Despite the fact that prior study has shown that POS creates a positive work environment for employees, the impact of POS on workplace conflict has been disregarded.

VI. CONCLUSION

The notion of Perceived Organizational Support will assist in identifying essential features and their contributions to organisational core competence improvement. It will also make developing a theoretical model for evaluating future employee-employer relationships easier. It will give advice on how to improve the interaction between management and employees. The concept of Perceived Organizational Support will aid in identifying key characteristics and

their contributions to improving organisational core competence. It will also make it easier to construct a theoretical model for assessing future employee-employer relationships. It will offer suggestions on how to improve management-employee engagement. By linking employee perceptions of a variety of HR practises to POS, this study adds to the literature on human resource management and organisational behaviour. It also offers advice on how organisations can foster high levels of perceived support through the implementation of appropriate HR practises. The strong effects of POS on essential job outcomes highlight the value of POS research and the need for firms to provide appropriate assistance to their employees. Furthermore, the fact that employee reactions to POS differed depending on their level of professional dedication emphasises the importance of academics accounting for individual differences in POS research and businesses paying attention to their employees' professional demands and attitudes. When managers are concerned about their employees' commitment to the organisation, employees are concerned about the organization's commitment to them, according to a study on perceived organisational support. Employees gain from socio-emotional resources like respect and caring, as well as tangible rewards like pay and health insurance. Because POS is such a novel concept, questions about its distinctiveness from other ideas have been raised, and additional research on its contribution to organisational excellence through high employee productivity has to be done. Finally, initiatives for improving perceived organisational support are linked to the employee-organizational connection. Because employee perceptions of organisational support influence their attributions to organisational behaviour, which in turn guide their job attitudes and behaviour, HR departments must understand the measures that can improve employee perceptions of organisational support, formulate organisational support programmes prior to employment, continuously monitor employee perceptions of organisational support, and take corrective action as needed.

REFERENCES

- ABaron,R.danD.B.(2003).PsikologiSosial.Jakarta:Airlangga.
- Abdul Rahim.(2013).Investment, Board Governance and Firm Value: A Panel Data Analysis.International Review of Business ResearchPapers, 6(5),.
- Alwisol.(2004). Psikologi Kepribadian. Malang: UMPress.
- Ance Selfi Adianita, S. M. dan C. (2017). Kompetensi Karyawan, Emotional Quotient dan Self Efficacy Pengaruhnyaterhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior dan Kinerja Karyawanpada Indo mobil Grupdi Surabaya Journal of Research in Economics and Management. Jurnal Riset Ekonomi Dan Manajemen, 17,No.1.
- Ari Fadzilah. (2006). Analisis Pengaruh Pemberdayaan Karyawan dan Self Of Efficacy terhadap kinerja karyawan bagian penjualan pada PT. Sinar Sosro Wilayah pemasaran semarang.
- AsamuFestusFemi.(2014).TheimpactofcommunicationonWorker'sperformanceinselectedorganizationsin LagosState,Nigeria.JournalOfHumanitiesAndSocialScience(IOSR-JHSS),Vol.19.N.
- Bandura, A. (1994). Self-efficacy. In V. S. Ramachaudran (Ed.), Encyclopedia of human behavior, 4, 71–81.
- Baron&DonnByrne.(2003).PsikologiSosial.Jakarta:Erlangga.